

RIG-I Activation and NKG2A Editing Synergize to Enhance NK Cell Antitumor Activity.

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Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1: HLA-E genotypes obtained by Sanger sequencing from genomic DNA of the *HLA-E*^{-/-} clones.

Cell Line	Clone	Indels	Genotype
A-431	#1	-1/-2	ATTCCACACTCCGTG(-T)CC / ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-GT)CC
	#2	-1/-1	ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGTG(-T)CC
	#3	-7/-2	ATTCCACAC(-TTCCGTG)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-GT)CC
A549	#1	-1/-1	ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC
	#2	-4/-4	ATTCCACACTTC(-CGTG)TCC / ATTCCACACTTC(-CGTG)TCC
	#3	-1/+1	ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGT(+T)TCC
SK-OV-3	#1	-1/-1	ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC
	#2	-1/-1	ATTCCACACTTCCG(-T)GTCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC
	#3	+1/-11	CGAG(+T)TCCGAGGATGGTGCCG / ACAA(-CGACGCCGCGA)GTCCGAGGATGG
EFO-21	#1	+1/+1	ATTCCACACTTCCGTG(+A)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGTG(+A)TCC
	#2	-1/+1	ATTCCACACTTCCGT(-G)TCC / ATTCCACACTTCCGTG(+T)TCC
	#3	-2/-4	ATTCCACACTTC(-CG)TGTCC / ATTCCACACTTCC(-GTGT)CC
CACO-2	#1	-52/-52	AGTATTC(- CACACTTCCGTGTCCCGGCCGGCCGCGGGGAGC CCCGCTTCATCTCTGTGG)GCTACGTGGA
	#2	-88/-88	CACTTCCGTG(-TCCCGGCCGGCCGCGGGGAGCCCCGCTTCA TCTCTGTGGGCTACGTGGACGACACCCAGTTCGTGCGCTTCGAC AACGACGCCGCGA)GTCCGAGG
	#3	-88/-88	CACTTCCGTG(-TCCCGGCCGGCCGCGGGGAGCCCCGCTTCA TCTCTGTGGGCTACGTGGACGACACCCAGTTCGTGCGCTTCGAC AACGACGCCGCGA)GTCCGAGG

Supplementary Table 2: KIR and HLA-I expression by NK donors, and figures in which the donors were used.

Number	Sex	KIR	HLA-I	Figures	
1	F	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, Bw4	CAPAN2 Match	A431 3DL1 MM
2	F	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, Bw4	CAPAN2 Match	A431 3DL1 MM
3	M	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1	CAPAN2 Match	
4	F	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, A3/11, Bw4	CAPAN2 MM	
5	F	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, A3/11, Bw4	CAPAN2 MM	
6	F	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, A3/11	CAPAN2 MM	
7	F	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, Bw4	CAPAN2 Match	A431 3DL1 MM
8	M	2DL1, 2DL2, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, A3/11, Bw4	CAPAN2 MM	
9	F	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, A3/11, Bw4	CAPAN2 MM	
10	M	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, A3/11	A431 Match	
11	F	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, A3/11	A431 Match	
12	M	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, A3/11	A431 Match	
13	M	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, A3/11	A431 Match	
14	F	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, Bw4	A431 MM	CAPAN2 2DL1 MM
15	F	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, Bw4	A431 MM	CAPAN2 2DL1 MM
16	F	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, Bw4	A431 MM	CAPAN2 2DL1 MM
17	M	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, Bw4	A431 MM	CAPAN2 2DL1 MM
18	M	2DL1, 2DL2, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, C2, Bw4	A431 MM	
19	M	2DL1, 2DL3, 3DL1, 3DL2	C1, Bw4		A431 3DL1 MM

Supplementary Table 3: Primer sequences used for cloning HLA-E CDS into lentiviral plasmids, CRISPR Oligos for HLA-E, HLA-E genotyping, and qPCR.

Cloning Primers	
Name	Sequence
hsHLAESallFor	aaaagtcgacATGGTAGATGGAACCTCCTTTTAC
hsHLAENotIRev	aaaagcggccgcTTACAAGCTGTGAGACTCAGACCC
HLAECRISPROligo1	TGGAAAGGACGAAACACCGATTTCACACTTCCGTGTCCGTTTTAGAGCTA GAAATAGCA
HLAECRISPROligo3	TGGAAAGGACGAAACACCGCGGCACCATCCTCGGACTCGGTTTTAGAGCT AGAAATAGCA

Genotyping primers	
HLAE_T7_for	GATGGAAACGGCCTCTACCG
HLAE_T7_rev	CTGAGACTCTCCCCGGTCTA
qPCR Primers	
RT_hsHLAE_for	GCTGAGTGGAGCGACAGTG
RT_hsHLAE_rev	CAGAGGCCCTTGCAAAAAGAG
RT_hsGAPDH_for	CATCTTCCAGGAGCGAGATCCC
RT_hsGAPDH_rev	TTCACACCCATGACGAACAT
RT_hsHLAG_for	TCATGGGTATCGTTGCTGGC
RT_hsHLAG_rev	GGGCAGCTGTTTACATTGC
RT_hsfIT1_for	GTGCTTGAAGTGGACCCTGA
RT_hsfIT1_rev	CCTGCCCTAGGGGAAGCAAA
RT_hsCXCL10_for	CCACGTGTTGAGATCATTGCT
RT_hsCXCL10_rev	TGCATCGATTTTGTCCCCT

Supplementary Table 4: Antibodies and dilutions used for flow cytometry and immunoblotting experiments.

Flow Cytometry Antibodies	Dilution	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
PE anti-human HLA-E [3D12]	1:250	BioLegend	Cat# 342603, RRID:AB_1659250
Pacific Blue™ anti-human CD45 Antibody [HI30]	1:250	BioLegend	BioLegend Cat# 304029, RRID:AB_2174123
PE/Cy7® anti-human HLA-E [3D12]	1:200	BioLegend	BioLegend Cat# 342608, RRID:AB_2565263
Brilliant Violet 510™ anti-human HLA-A,B,C [W6/32]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 311436, RRID:AB_2566255
FITC anti-human HLA-A,B,C [W6/32]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 311404, RRID:AB_314873
APC anti-human CD159a (NKG2A) [REA110]	1:300	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-113-563, RRID:AB_2726170
PE anti-human CD158a (KIR2DL1) Antibody [HP-DM1]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 374904, RRID:AB_2832736
PE anti-human CD158b (KIR2DL2/DL3) [DX27]	1:200	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-092-618, RRID:AB_871610
PE anti-human CD158b2 (KIR2DL3) [REAfinity™ REA147]	1:200	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-100-121, RRID:AB_2655336
PE-anti-human CD158e1 (KIR3DL1, NK1) [DX9]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 312708, RRID:AB_2249498
PE anti-human CD45 Antibody [HI30]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 304008, RRID:AB_314396
FITC anti-human CD3 [UCHT1]	1:100	BD Biosciences	Cat# 555332, RRID:AB_395739
FITC anti-human CD19 [HIB19]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 302206, RRID:AB_314236
Brilliant Violet 510 anti-human CD16 [3G8]	1:200	BD Biosciences	Cat# 563830, RRID:AB_2938676
APC anti-human CD69 [FN50]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 310910, RRID:AB_314845
FITC anti-human KIR2D [NKVFS1]	1:200	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-098-689, RRID:AB_2660018

PE/Cy7 [®] anti-human CD314 (NKG2D) [1D11]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 320812, RRID:AB_2234394
PE anti-human CD159c (NKG2C) [S19005E]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 375004, RRID:AB_2888871
Brilliant Violet 421™ anti-human TIGIT (VSTM3) [A15153G]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 372710, RRID:AB_2632925
BV605 anti-human CD337 (NKp30) [p30-15 (RUO)]	1:200	BD Biosciences	Cat# 563384, RRID:AB_2738170
PE anti-human CD336 (NKp44) [44.189]	1:200	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 12-3369-42, RRID:AB_2572607
Super Bright 702 anti-human CD8a	1:200	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 67-0087-41, RRID:AB_2735025
PE anti-human CD137 (4-1BB) [4B4-1]	1:200	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 12-1379-42, RRID:AB_1272083
PE/Cy7 [®] anti-human CD337 (NKp30) [AF29-4D12]	1:200	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 25-3379-42, RRID:AB_2573446
PE/Cy7 [®] anti-human CD279 (PD-1) [J105]	1:200	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 25-2799-42, RRID:AB_10853804
PE anti-human CD107a (LAMP-1) [H4A3]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 328608, RRID:AB_1186040
Antibodies for intracellular staining			
PE/Cy7 [®] anti-human TNF-a [MAb11]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 502930, RRID:AB_2204079
Pacific Blue™ anti-Granzyme B [clone: GB11]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 515408, RRID:AB_2562196
FITC anti-human Perforin [dG9]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 308104, RRID:AB_314702
Apc/cy7 anti-human IFN-γ [B27]	1:200	BioLegend	Cat# 506524, RRID:AB_2566136
Antibodies used for immunoblotting			
mouse anti-HLA E antibody [MEM-E/02]	1:1000	Abcam	Cat# ab2216, RRID:AB_302895
mouse anti-HLA-G [4H84]	1:1000	Santa Cruz Biotechnology	Cat# sc-21799, RRID:AB_627938
rabbit anti-human B-Tubulin [9F3]	1:1000	Cell Signaling Technology	Cat# 2128, RRID:AB_823664
Donkey Anti-Rabbit IgG Polyclonal Antibody (IRDye [®] 680RD)	1:15000	LI-COR Biosciences	Cat# 926-68073, RRID:AB_10954442
Goat Anti-Mouse IgG (H + L)-HRP Conjugate	1:3000	Bio-Rad	Cat# 1706516, RRID:AB_2921252
Goat Anti-Mouse IgG Polyclonal Antibody (IRDye [®] 800CW)	1:15000	LI-COR Biosciences	Cat# 926-32210, RRID:AB_621842

Resources table:

REAGENT		
Human Cell Lines	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
721.221	Prof. Dr. Carsten Watzl. IfADo	CVCL_6263
A-431	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	AAC 91
A549	Institute of Clinical Chemistry and Clinical Pharmacology	CVCL_A549

JEG-3	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	AAC 463
Caco-2	Institute of Clinical Chemistry and Clinical Pharmacology	CVCL_0025
PANC-1	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	AAC 783
Capan-2	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	AAC 245
HT-29	Institute of Clinical Chemistry and Clinical Pharmacology	CVCL_0320
EFO-21	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	AAC 235
K-562	Institute of Clinical Chemistry and Clinical Pharmacology	CVCL_0004
SK-OV-3	American Type Culture Collection (ATCC)	HTB-77
U-2 OS	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	ACC 785
NK-92	Leibniz Institute DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH	ACC 488
293FT Invitrogen TM	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# R70007
IFN- α/β Reporter HEK 293 Cells	Invivogen	Cat# hkb-ifnabv2
Cell Culture Reagents		
EasySep Direct Human NK Isolation Kit	STEMCELL Technologies	Cat# 19665
NK MACS Medium, human	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-114-429
Human Serum off-the-clot, Type AB, male, sterile filtered	PAN Biotech	Cat# P40-2702
RPMI 1640	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 21875091
Penicillin-Streptomycin (10000 U/ml)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 15140122
Fetal Bovine Serum	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# A5256701
DMEM, high glucose	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 41965062
L-glutamine 200 mM	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 25030081
MEM non-essential amino acids solution (100X)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 11140050
Sodium Pyruvate (100 mM)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 11360070
IMDM	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 12440053
Trypsin-EDTA (0.25%)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 25200056
Trypsin-EDTA (0.05%)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 25300096
McCoy's 5A (Modified) Medium	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 16600082
MEM α , nucleosides	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 22571-038
Advanced DMEM/F-12	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 12634010

Commercial assays	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
KIR Typing Kit	Miltenyi Biotec	Cat# 130-092-584
Bd humanifn γ ELISA Set	BD Biosciences	Cat# 555142, RRID:AB_2869029
Chemical, peptides and recombinant proteins		
Recombinant human IL-2	ImmunoTools	Cat# 11340027
Recombinant human IL-15	ImmunoTools	Cat# 11340155
Recombinant human IFN-gamma	ImmunoTools	Cat# 11343536
Recombinant human IFN-alpha2a	ImmunoTools	Cat# 11343506
Alt-R® S.p. HiFi Cas9 Nuclease V3	Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT	Cat# 1081061
TranscriptAid T7 High yield transcription kit	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# K0441
Poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate), BioReagent, powder, suitable for cell culture	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat# P3932-10G
Monensin Solution (1,000X)	BioLegend	Cat# 420701
Brefeldin A Solution (1,000X)	BioLegend	Cat# 420601
Y-27632 2HCl	Selleck Chemicals	Cat# s1049
Buffer RLT (220 ml)	Qiagen	Cat#79216
Buffer RW1 (220 ml)	Qiagen	Cat#1053394
RNA Wash Buffer (24 ml)	Zymo Research	Cat#R1003-3-24
DNase I, RNase-frei (1 U/ μ l)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat#EN0521
RevertAid Reverse Transcriptase (200 U/ μ L)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat#EP0442
my-Budget 5x EvaGreen (R) QPCR-Mix II (ROX)	Bio-Budget Technologies	Cat#80-5820000
Lipofectamine 2000 Reagent	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 11668019
eBioscience™ Fixable Viability Dye eFluor™ 780	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 65-0865-18
Molecular Probes FAST DiO Solid; DiO Δ	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# D3898
Zombie NIR™ Fixable Viability Kit	BioLegend	Cat# 423106
Animal-Free Recombinant Human EGF	Proteintech	Cat# AF-100-15
Animal-free Recombinant Human HGF	Proteintech	Cat# HZ-1084
[Leu15]-Gastrin I human, \geq 95% (HPLC)	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat# G9145-.5MG
Corning® Matrigel® Matrix, Phenol Red Free, Corning®, Matrigel Matrix GFR PhenolRF Mouse	Corning	Cat# 356231
TransIT®-LT1 Transfection Reagent	Mirus Bio	Cat# MIR2305
HEPES 1M	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 15-630-106
Normocin 500 mg	Invivogen	Cat# ant-nr-1
Amphotericin B	Biowest	Cat# L0009-100
Forskolin	Tocris	Cat# 1099
A-83-01	Tocris	Cat# 2939

B-27™ Supplement (50X), minus vitamin a	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Cat# 12-587-010
Corning® Cell Recovery Solution	Corning	Cat# 354253
Oligonucleotides		
Alt-R® CRISPR-Cas9 Negative Control crRNA #1	Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT	Cat# 1072544
Alt-R™ Cas9 Electroporation Enhancer	Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT	Cat# 10007805
Alt-R® CRISPR-Cas9 tracrRNA	Integrated DNA Technologies, IDT	Cat# 1072534
Poly(I:C) (HMW)	Invivogen	Cat# tlr1-pic
Deoxyribonucleic acid sodium salt from herring testes, Type XIV	Sigma-Aldrich	Cat# D6898-1G